

THE CONCEPT AND MEANING OF ARTISTIC IMAGE IN FINE ARTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the multifaceted meaning and significance of the artistic image in the fine arts. The introduction discusses the importance of images for the visual arts and highlights the objectives of the study. The main part shows the theoretical aspects, the creation process, the functional purpose and the current state of the artistic image. The influence of modern technologies and new media on the creation of artistic images, as well as the problems and prospects of modern art are considered. In conclusion, the results of the study are summed up, the importance of the artistic image in the fine arts for contemporary art is emphasized, and the prospects for further research are discussed.*

Keywords: *artistic image, fine art, creativity, aesthetic perception, creative thinking, spirituality, philosophy of art, cultural significance, contemporary art, movement.*

In the world of art, there is a single universal language that overcomes the barriers of time, culture and language - this is the language of artistic images. It is an integral part of our cultural essence, it embodies the feelings, thoughts and ideas of the creators and takes us to worlds where words are superfluous.

An artistic image is not just an image on fabric or paper. It is a hidden language that speaks to us through colors, shapes and compositions. We will study its aesthetic essence, role in communication and self-expression, and enter the special world of the artistic image. We'll look at how it serves not only as a visual tool, but also as a powerful tool for communication, inspiration, and self-expression.

From ancient sculptures to modern multimedia installations, artistic images continue to inspire surprise, delight and even controversy. In this article we will look at the role of the artistic image as the main element of fine art and get acquainted with its aesthetic, emotional and cultural significance. By studying this topic, we will see how an artistic image becomes not only a reflection of the world around us, but also an instrument for changing it, inspiring us to see and fill the surrounding reality with new depth and beauty.

The main goal of our article is to analyze the concept of an artistic image and determine its meaning in the field of fine art. We strive to understand its theoretical aspects, study the methods of its creation, and analyze its functions in the process of perceiving and understanding art. Our analysis provides students with theoretical information about the essence of the artistic image and its important place in the art world.

In fine art, an image is a visual image created by an artist using various artistic tools such as lines, colors, shapes, and textures to convey a specific meaning or feeling. - described. It can be an abstract or realistic image that evokes an emotional or intellectual response in the viewer. An artistic image can be depicted on fabric, paper, stone, wood, metal and other materials and in various forms of art, including painting, sculpture, graphics and photography.

The concept of an artistic image has its historical roots and has been formed over centuries. In ancient times, images were often used to depict gods, heroes, or historical events based on mythological or religious views and ideas. Over time, the concept of artistic image became abstract, allowing artists to express their thoughts, emotions and feelings through form, color and composition.

In the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, the artistic image acquired a new form and meaning, becoming not only a means of religious veneration, but also a way of studying human nature and beauty. In subsequent centuries, the concept of artistic image continued to evolve, reflecting changing movements and cultural trends in art along with various events. Today, the concept of artistic image continues to evolve in the field of contemporary art, including new technologies and media such as computer graphics and video art. At the same time, it retains its significance as a way of expressing and perceiving the world around us.

Philosophical and cultural roots have a significant influence on the formation of an artistic image, giving its content color, symbolism and emotional depth. Let's look at the main aspects of this effect:

For many artists and writers, philosophical concepts and ideas such as ethics, metaphysics, and the study of human nature and society were often the basis of their artistic creations. Artistic images often express the concepts of good and evil, freedom and fate, the meaning of life and immortality. Philosophy can serve as a source of inspiration for artists, helping them express their thoughts and feelings through images and symbols. For example, the philosophy of existentialism had a significant influence on literature and art of the 20th century, creating works about the meaning of life, freedom and responsibility.

Religious beliefs and mythological ideas play an important role in the formation of an artistic image. Religious beliefs and mythological ideas can be incorporated into artistic images. Many artists and writers are inspired by religious stories, cultural legends or various rituals to create images with deep philosophical meaning. Myths and legends, folk tales and mythological characters often become central elements of art. They not only inspire artists with their vibrant images, but also serve as a means of transmitting cultural heritage and traditions. Many cultures have a rich heritage of myths and religious imagery, which are often used in art to convey certain ideas or feelings.

Artistic images often reflect the historical and sociocultural characteristics of a certain period or society. For example, Renaissance art reflects the ideals of its time, including humanism and an interest in classical art and science. Socio-cultural conditions also influence the formation of an artistic image. Political events, social movements, cultural trends - all of this can be reflected in the work of artists and create images that reflect the spirit of the time and evoke opinions among viewers. All these factors together help create multi-layered and deep artistic images that are not only aesthetically attractive, but also rich in content and symbolism. The interaction of philosophy, religion, mythology and the sociocultural sphere creates the richness and diversity of the artistic world and makes it a constant source of inspiration and research for viewers and researchers.

Artistic imagery, whether in literature, visual arts, music or other art forms, often has deep philosophical and cultural roots. Artists and writers can draw inspiration from personal experiences, ideas, and imagination. This may be the personal experience of a particular author or the collective experience of a society or culture. Many works of art are symbolic or allegorical, expressing something deeper or abstract through certain images, themes, or symbols. Together or

separately, these factors can influence the formation of an artistic image, make it rich and multifaceted in content, and influence the viewer or reader.

The role of the artistic image in aesthetic perception is an important aspect of art; it has a deep impact on the viewer and determines his emotional and intellectual experiences. Artistic images can evoke pleasure, excitement, anxiety, sadness and many other emotions in the viewer. This occurs through the use of color, composition, light and shadows that create atmosphere and mood in a work of art. Artistic images often contain deep meaning and symbolism that provoke thought and analysis in the viewer. They may represent allegories, metaphors, or abstract ideas that require interpretation and discovery by the viewer. An artistic image can be pleasing in itself for its beauty, harmony and balance. Aesthetic appreciation of art can come from visual pleasure in the shapes, lines, textures and proportions used in the work. Artistic images can serve as a means of communication between the artist and the viewer, allowing ideas, feelings and concepts to be conveyed through visual language. They can address universal themes and emotions, making them accessible to a wide audience. Works of art can awaken new thoughts, ideas and experiences in the viewer, thereby developing imagination and creative thinking, opening up new horizons of creativity.

The artistic image plays a key role in aesthetic perception, affecting the emotional, intellectual and even spiritual level of the viewer. This allows you not only to enjoy the beauty of art, but also to enrich the viewer's inner world by interacting with the work.

The creation of artistic images in different artistic directions can be carried out using different styles and methods. Here are some of the basic methods and techniques that artists use to create images in various forms of art:

- *Realism*: - close attention to detail and the desire for the most realistic depiction of objects. Using light, shadow and contrast to create dimension and depth in an image.

- *Impressionism*: -the use of short strokes (painting) to create the effect of light and movement. Bright and saturated colors are used next to each other to create the impression of reflections of light and color.

- *Expressionism*: - the use of expressive lines and shapes to convey an emotional state or mood. The use of bright and unusual colors will emphasize the emotional richness of the product.

- *Cubism*: - dividing objects into geometric shapes to create abstract compositions. Creating a composition from different parts using collage gives this piece a fragmented and dynamic character.

- *Surrealism*: - creating images based on imagination, dreams and legends. Creating unreal and mysterious images by combining unusual elements and associations.

These methods and techniques are part of the techniques that artists can use to create images in different artistic styles. Each work has its own characteristics and techniques that allow artists to express their ideas and impressions in accordance with their creative vision. The influence of technique and material on the formation of an image in the artistic process can be significant, since the choice of a particular technique and material affects the visual and emotional characteristics of the image, and one of the main aspects of this impact is texture. and surfaces where different materials have different effects on the artistic image have a variety of textural properties that can be used to create effects. For example, the rough surface of fabric can create a more textured and tactile appearance than the smooth surface of paper.

In colors and shades, the artistic image is influenced by the color palette, overall essence and feel of the appearance. Watercolor has richer and deeper shades than, for example, acrylic paint. In particular, different techniques provide different ways of creating an image. For example, watercolor allows you to create transparent and light layers of paint, which is useful for creating effects of transparency and light, while watercolor allows you to create denser, more saturated images.

In addition, each material and technique has its own expressive capabilities, with the help of which one can express certain feelings and moods in an artistic image. For example, rough and rough strokes or brushstrokes can create a feeling of dynamism and movement, while soft and smooth transitions create a feeling of calm and harmony. Using different materials and techniques can inspire the artist's experiences and ideas, resulting in unique and original images. For example, mixing different materials or using unconventional creation methods can lead to unexpected and unique results.

In general, the choice of technique and material plays a key role in shaping the image in the visual arts, since together they determine the visual and emotional characteristics of the work, as well as its expressiveness and originality.

Let's look at a few examples of famous artistic images to analyze the styles and methods of creating an artistic image, as well as the aesthetic effect:

Leonardo da Vinci's painting "Mona Lisa".

Leonardo da Vinci used mixed media, including oil on wood panel. He also created smooth transitions between colors and contours using the “sfumato” technique (Italian sfumato “foggy, unclear, cloudy” ← Latin fumus “smoke, fog”), giving the image softness and realism.

Mona Lisa is known for her mysterious smile and interesting gaze that follows what is happening around her. Its subtle features and soft light create an atmosphere of mystery and elegance.

Painting "Starry Night" by Vincent Van Gogh.

Van Gogh used watercolor on canvas and expressive brush strokes to convey his vision of the night sky. Therefore, he used bright and saturated colors to create the impression of movement and energy.

“The Starry Night” has rapid dynamics and a rich color palette, creating a feeling of mysticism and excitement. This image evokes in the viewer a feeling of delight and wonder at the majestic beauty of the night sky.

Sculpture of Lysippos "Hercules and the Lion".

The artistic image of this sculptor is made of marble and is an example of ancient Greek art. Lysippos used great skill in working with marble and created the image of a strong and brave Hercules fighting a lion.

The sculpture “Hercules and the Lion” impresses with its proportions, dynamics of movements and detailed elaboration of muscles and anatomical details. Its aesthetic effect is a symbol of heroism and victory over evil forces.

These examples show how a variety of artistic techniques and materials can be used to create images that have a strong aesthetic impact and evoke a wide range of emotions in the viewer. Each of these images has its own aesthetic value and symbolic meaning, and it is these aspects that make them famous and valuable works of art.

In general, the communicative function of an artistic image lies in its ability to convey information, feelings and ideas from the artist to the viewer, establishing an important interaction between them. This function is one of the main aspects of the artistic process and makes images an important means of communication and interaction in the art world. The symbolic function of an artistic image lies in its ability to convey hidden meanings, ideas and concepts through symbols, metaphors and allegories.

Artists may use different symbols that have known meanings and meanings in a culture or society. For example, a dove can be a symbol of peace, an apple a symbol of knowledge, and a rose a symbol of love. By including such symbols in their works, artists can enrich the images with hidden meanings and content.

Thanks to its symbolic function, an artistic image becomes not only a carrier of feelings and beauty, but also a means of conveying deep ideas and concepts that can have a significant impact on the perception and understanding of the work. This feature allows the artist to create images that can be interpreted and experienced by the viewer at different levels of meaning. The aesthetic task of an artistic image is its ability to evoke emotional reactions and influence the emotional state of the viewer through the visual and aesthetic features of the work of art.

Viewing beautiful and interesting artistic images can bring aesthetic pleasure and joy to the viewer. Works of art are a source of inspiration and positive emotions for the viewer; they lift his spirits and improve his emotional state. Artistic images evoke a vivid imagination in the viewer and develop his imagination. Thanks to its aesthetic function, an artistic image becomes not only an object of perception, but also a source of emotional and aesthetic pleasure for the viewer. This allows the work of art to influence the viewer's feelings and perceptions, making their experience deeper, richer and more meaningful.

He made significant changes in the understanding and use of artistic image in modern art. In the sphere of artistic creativity, there is not only a change in images, but also a change in their role, function and methods of perception. Artists are increasingly turning to abstraction and experimenting with form, color, texture and space. The images are less clear and represent compositions and impressions rather than actual images. This opens up new possibilities for creative expression and interpretation for both artist and viewer.

With the development of visual technologies, modern artists are increasingly using multimedia formats and digital technologies to create artistic images. This may include computer graphics, interactive installations, virtual worlds and more. Such images are more dynamic, interactive and multidimensional, opening up new opportunities for visual exploration and perception. Contemporary artistic imagery often serves as a means of expressing social, political and cultural commentary and criticism. Artists use images to explore pressing themes and issues in contemporary society and to stimulate dialogue and reflection.

These changes in the concept of image in contemporary art reflect a wide range of innovative approaches and trends emerging in the world of contemporary art. They open up new horizons of creativity and perception, forming innovations in communication and art.

Technology and new media are playing an increasingly important role in the contemporary artistic process, opening up new possibilities for creativity and experimentation. With the advancement of computer graphics and software, artists can use new tools to create images. Digital software allows artists to create highly detailed images, manipulate colors and shapes, and apply various effects and filters to achieve the desired aesthetic effect.

Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) allow artists to create immersive and interactive works of art that immerse the viewer in a virtual or augmented space. This includes creating virtual art galleries, interactive installations, and even virtual sculptures.

Artists are increasingly using multimedia technologies to create installations and projections that combine various art forms such as fine art, sculpture, sound and video. This allows for the creation of multi-layered and multi-faceted works of art that enrich the viewer's perception and awaken his emotions and imagination. With the rise of social media and digital platforms, artists have new ways to share their work and interact with audiences. They can create digital portfolios, participate in online exhibitions and projects, and receive feedback and support from a community of artists and art lovers.

Digital technologies allow artists to experiment with new formats, materials and techniques. With the rise of social media and digital platforms, artists have new opportunities to connect and collaborate with their peers and audiences, share ideas and experiences, and receive feedback and support. Technologies and new media open up wide opportunities for creators, allow them to experiment with new formats, materials and techniques, and expand their creative horizons. It serves the development of contemporary art, enriching the cultural landscape with new ideas and expressions.

In the era of digital technology, the artistic image, along with the opening of new directions, simultaneously faces various difficulties. With the development of digital technology and software, some artists are faced with the problem of losing the authenticity of their work. The processes of creating and distributing artistic images are becoming increasingly digital, which can distance a work from its physical history and identity. With the digital distribution of works of art, new problems arise in the field of copyright and intellectual property protection. Digital copies of works can be easily distributed and copied without the artist's permission, which may result in a loss of control over the use and distribution of the work.

Contemporary art practice is increasingly reliant on specialized hardware and software, which can pose challenges for artists with insufficient technical skills or equipment. In the era of digital technology, access to artistic images is becoming increasingly wider and more diverse, which creates problems of attracting the attention of viewers to a particular work of art in conditions of information noise and oversaturation.

In conclusion, we can emphasize the importance of the artistic image for modern art in terms of its versatility, depth and impressiveness. The creation of an artistic image includes a variety of styles and techniques: from traditional artistic styles to the use of modern technologies and new media, the artistic image performs a variety of functions, including communicative, symbolic and aesthetic, which give it an emotional state. viewer and allows you to influence perception.

The artistic image is a central element of the visual arts and plays an important role in the communication between the artist and the viewer, in the transmission of feelings, ideas and concepts. Philosophical, cultural and social aspects have a significant impact on the formation and interpretation of an artistic image, enriching its semantic depth and diversity. Contemporary art brings new challenges and opportunities for the artistic image, including changes in its concept, the use of new technologies and media, and the expansion of its sociocultural context.

In general, the artistic image remains a central element of modern art, embodying the creative actions, ideas and inspiration of the artist, as well as causing reactions, reflections and perceptions in the viewer. Its significance and power remain incomparable in the context of the evolution and diversity of contemporary art. And digital technology allows artists to distribute their work around the world, giving them new opportunities to interact and engage with global audiences and audiences.

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